

TABLE-1 ANALYTICAL DATA ELECTRICAL CONDUCTANCES (OHM⁻¹CM²MOLE⁻¹ IN 95% ETHANOL AT 308°K) AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS (308°K)

S No	Complex	Colour	Elemental Analyses								Conductance	μ_B
			% Cr		% C		% H		% N			
			Found	Reqd	Found	Reqd	Found	Reqd	Found	Reqd		
1	[Cr(PyBzH)(NCS) ₂ OH H ₂ O] 1 5C ₈ H ₉ OH	Brown	11.20	11.12	43.23	43.67	4.14	4.53	15.40	14.98	12.0	3.83
2	[Cr(HO-PhBzH)(O-PhBzH)(NCS) ₂] 3C ₈ H ₉ OH	Bluish green	7.19	7.16	56.74	56.26	4.72	5.14	12.19	11.58	37.0	3.65
3	[Cr(H ₂ N-PhBzH)(H ₂ N-PhBz)(NCS) ₂] 2 5C ₈ H ₉ OH 3H ₂ O	Brown	6.93	6.89	52.98	52.49	5.75	5.61	14.91	14.84	16.0	3.66
4	[Cr(H ₂ N-PhBzH)(NCS) ₂ OH H ₂ O] 2C ₈ H ₉ OH 3H ₂ O	Reddish pink	10.00	9.78	43.41	42.92	5.23	5.50	13.00	13.17	25.0	*

* could not be determined on account of very low yield of the complex

calibrated with Hg[Co(NCS)₄]⁹, diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants¹⁰. Electronic absorption spectra were recorded on Beckman DK-2A Ratio Recording Spectrophotometer using matched silica cells. The infra-red spectra were scanned on Beckman IR-20 and IR-12 Spectrophotometers in KBr discs.

Results and Discussion

Thiocyanate groups are only partially replaced by the bidentate benzimidazoles under investigation and the stoichiometry of the compounds are shown in table 1, which are supported by their electrical conductance values. 2-(2-Pyridyl)benzimidazole coordinates through the two tertiary nitrogen atoms, the imidazole-NH remaining intact, this is in contrast to the observations made in the binuclear halo-bridged chromium(III) complexes with this ligand reported earlier⁸. The phenolic OH of one 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzimidazole molecule in the bis-chelate is presumably deprotonated. 2-(2-Aminophenyl)benzimidazole gives rise to two chelates: (i) a bis-chelated brown complex containing one deprotonated and the other undeprotonated ligand molecule, and (ii) a mono-chelated reddish pink complex containing an undeprotonated ligand.

As expected for a 3d³ ion with a ground state term, the room-temperature magnetic moment values (table 1) indicate the existence of chromium(III) in octahedral environment without any appreciable orbital- or TIP-contribution.

Infra-red Spectra

The infra-red spectrum of each complex has been

compared with that of the ligand and important observations have been noted in table 2.

The NH stretching frequencies of the ligands, which lie between 3010 and 3040 cm⁻¹, are shifted to higher frequency side in the complexes by 5-20 cm⁻¹. Harkins et al⁴ reported that there was a decrease in the NH stretching frequency of the pyridyl or the hydroxyphenyl derivatives on complexation with metals like copper(II), nickel(II), and zinc(II), but quite a good number of evidences has accumulated¹¹ to show that there is no regularity in this trend.

Strong CN stretching bands near 2065-2075 cm⁻¹ indicate N-bonded terminal thiocyanate. CS stretching frequency, which is more useful in distinguishing M-NCS and M-SCN isomers¹², were diagnostic¹ of M-NCS bonding in complexes with benzimidazole and 2-methylbenzimidazole. These bands, however, could not be identified in the complexes under present investigation as the out-of-plane bending mode of the 1,2-disubstituted aromatic rings or the pyridine nucleus at the 2-position of the imidazole ring also appeared in the same region¹³. The NCS bending has been more profitably used¹² in elucidating the linkage of thiocyanate group, N-bonded thiocyanate has this band near 450-490 cm⁻¹, whereas S-bonding lowers this to 400-440 cm⁻¹. The fact that all complexes under investigation show bands of medium intensity at 490 cm⁻¹ confirms the existence of N-bonded thiocyanate groups, which is in accordance with the general view that elements of the first transition series form M-NCS bonds rather than M-SCN ones¹².

TABLE 2—INFRA RED FREQUENCIES (CM⁻¹) IN KBR DISCS AND ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION BANDS (CM⁻¹) IN 95% ETHANOL

S No	Complex	NH Stretching*	Thiocyanate Vibrations		⁴ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (10D _q)
			ν (CN)	δ (NCS)	
1	[Cr(PyBzH)(NCS) ₂ OH H ₂ O] 1 5C ₈ H ₉ OH	3060 s (3040)	2065 vs	490 m	18 420
2	[Cr(HO-PhBzH)(O-PhBzH)(NCS) ₂] 3C ₈ H ₉ OH	3035 s (3030)	2070 vs	490 m	18 180
3	[Cr(H ₂ N-PhBzH)(H ₂ N-PhBz)(NCS) ₂] 2 5C ₈ H ₉ OH 3H ₂ O	3040 s (3025)	2075 vs	490 m	19 050
4	[Cr(H ₂ N-PhBzH)(NCS) ₂ OH H ₂ O] 2C ₈ H ₉ OH 3H ₂ O	3045 s (3025)	2070 vs	490 m	18 690

*NH Stretching frequencies of organic ligands in parentheses
Abbreviations vs=very strong s=strong m=medium intensity

Electronic Spectra

The electronic spectra (table 2) exhibit only one band on account of the transition ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ near 525-550 nm in each complex. The $10Dq$ values of these complexes are higher than that of $\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_6^{-3}$ ($17,800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and so, presumably, the substitution takes place easily. A comparison of the hydroxo-aquo-complexes of PyBzH and $\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{PhBzH}$ and diisothiocyanato-complexes of $\text{HO}-\text{PhBzH}$ and $\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{PhBzH}$ suggest the following relative positions of these ligands in spectrochemical series $\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{PhBzH} \sim \text{PyBzH} > \text{HO}-\text{PhBzH}$.

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